

FINAL REPORT

DIRECT

**CO-INNOVATION OF DIGITAL REHABILITATION IN
THE GLOBAL MARKETPLACE**

JOINT EFFORT BY

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The Institute of Rehabilitation is a part of Jyväskylä University of Applied Sciences (JAMK), The School of Health and Social Studies. The institute is a centre for education, development, and research in the field of multidisciplinary rehabilitation. Presently over 1000 students study rehabilitation and institute has over 25 RDI projects shaping the future of rehabilitation in Finland and beyond.

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Globally, an estimated 2.6 billion people are currently living with a health condition that benefits from rehabilitation (WHO).

“Digital Rehabilitation is not just scale. It’s disruption. The present model cannot grow fast enough to meet global demand. We’ve proven the potential of digital-first rehabilitation to scale basic rehabilitation service to all.”

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SUMMARY

The global demand for rehabilitation has surged by over 60% in recent decades, with more than 2 billion people currently in need [1]. This demand far exceeds the capacity of existing rehabilitation systems, especially in low- and middle-income countries. The World Health Organization has recognized rehabilitation as a core pillar of 21st century health systems and an important element in achieving Universal Health Coverage [2].

The DIRECT project was established to respond to this global challenge by creating and validating a scalable, digital-first rehabilitation model and solutions. Digital-first rehabilitation emphasizes using digital solutions as the first point of contact, and in certain cases, the primary avenue for delivering rehabilitation services. Project consortium was led by Jamk University of Applied Sciences, in collaboration with Physiotools Ltd. and CSE Entertainment Ltd., the project developed an interoperable digital rehabilitation service model, and a solution that can be adapted to different contexts and systems. The project tested and implemented a digital rehabilitation model in primary care settings in two East African and one Southeast Asian country. It engaged national ministries and reached thousands of global stakeholders through its dissemination efforts, all while maintaining rigorous research standards, ethical practices, and responsible innovation principles in close collaboration with private sector partners.

Over the course of the project, it achieved its core objectives:

- We partnered with local health authorities and stakeholders to develop a digital-first rehabilitation model, and key features were integrated into health system pilots.
- The community-based service delivery model served over 15,000 people and showed early signs of being both effective and affordable.
- Research demonstrates the model's scalability through improved outcomes (1.38 vs 0.47 QALYs) and considerable cost reductions.
- Professionals and users alike found the digital approach feasible, engaging, and relevant, with community health workers (CHWs) reporting increased confidence in care delivery and users experiencing improved access and autonomy in managing their rehabilitation.
- Global dissemination and engagement have established DIRECT as a leading example, evidenced by its case studies' recognition among global stakeholders and influence in policy conversations.

The project demonstrated that digital rehabilitation is not simply an extension of existing services, but a necessary disruption of conventional methods. By empowering communities, strengthening health systems, and generating internationally relevant evidence, DIRECT has laid the groundwork for sustainable, inclusive rehabilitation with potential to reach millions of more people. The outcomes provide a strong foundation for further advancement through national integration, expanded implementation across other social- and healthcare areas, and continued research into emerging opportunities, including AI-supported triage and multidisciplinary service pathways. While findings are promising, further validation across diverse contexts and longer-term follow-up are needed to assess sustainability and broader social- and health system integration.

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Key Findings and Recommendations

- 1. Digital-first rehabilitation is both effective and scalable:** Evidence from DIRECT shows that common rehabilitation needs (especially for musculoskeletal conditions) can be effectively addressed through community-level digital solutions. With improved health outcomes and significantly reduced costs (e.g. 1.38 vs. 0.47 QALYs, DR being 7x cheaper), digital rehabilitation should be integrated into global health financing and policy frameworks to expand access sustainably.
- 2. Task-sharing and digital tools can bridge the workforce gap:** The project demonstrated that community health workers (CHWs) can safely and effectively deliver basic physical rehabilitation interventions digitally under supervision. This model helps overcome the global shortage of rehabilitation professionals and should be included in workforce development strategies and UHC planning. Future phases should extend digital-first rehabilitation pilots to include other services beyond physical rehabilitation, such as cognitive, speech, and mental health interventions, where appropriate protocols and tools are available.
- 3. Local co-creation drives adoption and contextual fit:** The project's success was rooted in stakeholder co-design, aligning interventions with national priorities, community norms, and health system structures. Global implementers should prioritize participatory methods to ensure digital rehabilitation models are locally relevant, acceptable, and sustainable.
- 4. Global interest confirms readiness for paradigm shift:** Engagement with WHO secretariat, national ministries, and thousands of professionals through the Global Digital Rehabilitation Initiative forums and events signals a growing global interest towards digital rehabilitation. Continued international cooperation is needed to consolidate this shift and formalize digital rehabilitation in policy, training, and service delivery standards.
- 5. Evidence and an implementation model established:** The project combined real-world implementation with research and exploratory cost-effectiveness analysis. This dual approach is key to reducing risks associated with scaling up. Future investments should support integrated pilots that generate both service delivery outcomes and policy-relevant evidence. The use of the Framework for Accelerated and Systematic Technology-based intervention development and Evaluation Research (FASTER) [3] enabled rapid, iterative evidence-building alongside user engagement from the outset. The expansion of digital rehabilitation presents an opportunity to enhance efficiency through AI. For instance, fine-tuned large language models can assist CHWs in identifying needs and following up critical issues.
- 6. Integration, not isolation, ready for scale:** Digital rehabilitation should not be viewed in isolation but as a fundamental component of future rehabilitation systems. Aligning community-level digital interventions with facility-based services, data systems, and referral networks is essential for seamless, person-centered care. With proven feasibility, high-level endorsement, and emerging global frameworks (e.g. WHO Rehabilitation 2030 and Digital Health strategies), the time is right to institutionalize digital-first rehabilitation. More resources are needed for scale-up, capacity-building, and continued research to ensure millions more can benefit.
- 7. Private sector engagement and innovative models are key to sustainable scale:** The project showed that public-private collaboration can accelerate innovation, reduce implementation costs, and improve product-market fit. Finnish companies involved in the project were able to test, adapt, and validate their solutions through real-world pilots in diverse markets, supported by local ecosystems. To ensure scale and sustainability, future digital rehabilitation initiatives should involve private sector actors early and explore blended financing models, risk-sharing approaches, and integration with national insurance schemes. Innovation in business models, such as public-private partnerships, subscription-based service models, or telecom-supported delivery, will be essential to attract long-term investment and expand global access.

1. Introduction: The Need for Disruption

Rehabilitation is an essential, multidisciplinary service that enables individuals to optimize their functioning, participate fully in society, and live independently following illness, injury, or disability. Recognized by the World Health Organization as integral to achieving Universal Health Coverage, access to rehabilitation remains inadequate globally. An estimated 2.6 billion people worldwide live with health conditions that would benefit from rehabilitation, and this need is only increasing as populations age and chronic diseases rise [4]. Alarming, the majority of those in need do not currently receive appropriate care – in many low- and middle-income countries, over half of people cannot access the rehabilitation services they require. Based on our partner countries' estimates, probably less than 10% have direct access to quality rehabilitation services. In Indonesia and Vietnam, services are more available but not at primary care level.

This unmet need causes inequality in access to services for many, leading to prolonged disability, a lower quality of life, and societal productivity losses. Rehabilitation has therefore been recognized as essential to achieving universal health coverage and the health-related Sustainable Development Goals [4]. Addressing this gap calls for innovative approaches that can overcome traditional resource and workforce limitations. Digital rehabilitation and innovative service models have the potential to transform rehabilitation services.

Widespread connectivity and mobile technologies offer new ways for delivering interventions to clients outside clinical and specialized center environments. Global health authorities have highlighted that digital health solutions can make care more equitable, efficient, and accessible. However, applying digital tools and models of care effectively to rehabilitation requires rethinking service models and generating evidence for what works. The World Health Organization's Rehabilitation 2030 initiative emphasizes integrating rehabilitation across all levels of health systems and leveraging novel strategies to meet population needs [2].

In this context, a "digital-first" rehabilitation approach, where digital platforms and remote guidance serve as an initial mode of care delivery, has the potential to dramatically expand access to rehabilitation in underserved areas. Such an approach could empower existing social- and health workers to deliver basic rehabilitation interventions at scale, reserving specialist care for more complex cases. The DIRECT (Co-Innovation of Digital Rehabilitation in the Global Marketplace) project, launched in early 2022, set out to promote evidence-based digital rehabilitation services, develop replicable and scalable service models, and reduce critical disparities in access to multidisciplinary rehabilitation. A collaboration between JAMK University of Applied Sciences' Institute of Rehabilitation (Finland), Physiotoools Ltd. (now part of Physitrack), and CSE Entertainment Ltd., DIRECT received funding from Business Finland. The project operated internationally, with key pilot sites and collaborators in East Africa (notably Rwanda, Kenya, and Tanzania) and Asia (Indonesia and Vietnam). By co-innovating with local stakeholders such as the University of Rwanda's Centre of Excellence in Biomedical Engineering and eHealth (CEBE) and national Ministries of Health, DIRECT aimed to align its solutions with on-the-ground needs. The relevance and justification for the project was directly from the global rehabilitation service gap where millions lack the access needed. A bold, digitally-enabled paradigm shift is required. In summary, integrating digital models into rehabilitation is both timely and necessary to make it accessible to everyone, throughout their lives, as global health initiatives advocate.

The following sections detail how the DIRECT project implemented this initiative, what was achieved, and how it is catalyzing a new paradigm for rehabilitation services worldwide.

2. Project Implementation

Project design

The DIRECT project was implemented over 2022–2024 through a collaborative, multi-country approach. The work was organized into four main work packages (WPs) to systematically address different aspects of the innovation process. WP1 focused on overall project coordination and building global partnerships, ensuring that activities in each country remained aligned with the project plan. WP2 centered on developing a conceptual digital-first rehabilitation model integrated into health systems. WP3 dealt with evidence generation – researching and piloting digital rehabilitation in practice, and WP4 concentrated on global dissemination, and stakeholder engagement. This structured approach allowed the project to simultaneously pursue model development, practical trials, and broad acceptance.

Geographic scope and partners

Implementation took place in close partnership with local organizations in East Africa and Southeast Asia to ground the work in real-world contexts. Rwanda served as a flagship country for piloting the digital-first model, thanks to strong engagement from the Ministry of Health and the University of Rwanda/CEBE. Additional test-bed sites were in Kenya, Indonesia, and Vietnam to explore the model's adaptability. Tanzania was engaged at later stages. In each country, the project partnered with academic, rehabilitation associations or health institutions and obtained necessary governmental and/or institutional ethical approvals. In Rwanda, a national research permit and ethical clearance was received in 2022, making Rwanda the first country in the world to officially explore a digital-first rehabilitation service model at national level. This endorsement enabled close collaboration with Rwanda's health authorities and paved the way to have research test-beds in public primary care settings. Similar ethical approvals and partnerships were pursued in the other target countries, with local universities and healthcare providers based on requirements and scope.

The consortium approach, combining academia, private sector innovators, and multiple international collaborators, was a deliberate methodology to co-create solutions that are both evidence-based and practically relevant also in resource constrained environments.

Concept development

A cornerstone of the methodology was the participatory design of the digital-first rehabilitation conceptual model. Early in the project, WP2 conducted landscape analyses, professional and client interviews [5, 6, 7] to map existing rehabilitation services, policies, and gaps. These findings informed a draft model outlining how digital rehabilitation could be embedded into the social- and health system. Key elements of the model include task-sharing (enabling e.g. trained CHWs to guide basic rehabilitation exercise programs using a mobile application), integration with primary healthcare (linking digital rehabilitation activities with local health center supervision and referral pathways), and initially focusing on prevalent musculoskeletal conditions (e.g. low back pain). The draft conceptual model was validated and refined through engagement with policymakers and practitioners. For instance, Rwanda's Biomedical Centre arranged a rehabilitation task force meeting, including project researchers, to analyze the proposed model's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT analysis). Feedback from these sessions was used to iterate the model. Prior to finalization, the initial draft model underwent a pilot program in real healthcare settings (WP3), validating design principles through user feedback and feasibility assessments. This iterative, evidence-informed methodology aligns with agile co-innovation, a deliberate choice to keep the project implementation responsive to findings on the ground.

Methodology and Pilot Studies

To test and demonstrate the digital-first approach, DIRECT undertook several research activities and technology pilots in its target countries. These activities aligned with objectives of FASTER: 1) to expedite innovation in disability and rehabilitation, benefiting individuals and society, 2) to use diverse research methods and designs for technology-based interventions, and 3) to offer practical timely guidance for researchers, clinicians, and professionals integrating these interventions into practice [3].

Mixed-methods research was used, combining quantitative data (usage metrics, health outcomes) with qualitative insights (user experiences, implementation barriers). In Rwanda, the project introduced a digital rehabilitation pathway in select communities. In early 2023, 24 CHWs were recruited, trained, and provided with smartphones loaded with a mobile rehabilitation app (the Inclusion App, developed by Physiotools/Physitrack). These CHWs identified people with conditions like lower back pain that could benefit from rehabilitation and guided them through the application's exercise programs, thereby providing early rehabilitation in the community. The number of CHWs increased to 70 in 2024. Local physiotherapists and health centers provided referral support and oversight as needed. By late 2023, the Rwanda pilot spanned three districts, with CHWs attached to 5 health centers and 1 referral hospital for backup. In late 2024, the project enrolled clients in a cost-effectiveness study comparing the new digital and standard physiotherapy pathways in Rwanda.

Similarly, in Kenya, the team held workshops with rehabilitation professionals and community representatives to introduce the concept and gather baseline information on readiness for digital rehabilitation services. Pilot plans in Kenya involved integrating the Inclusion App into urban and rural settings through the CHW system. Implementation in Indonesia and Vietnam was context-specific; for instance, we partnered with a large Vietnamese private hospital to pilot digital exercise programs. Indonesia focused on primary care, with approximately 40 CHWs using the app during pilot programs. Additionally, an exergaming solution (from CSE Entertainment) was piloted in Indonesian commercial settings. The usability and feasibility of exergame solution was also explored in a Finnish special vocational school to support development and scaling up to user groups with special needs. Each country's activities were led or co-led by local research partners to ensure cultural and system fit. Standardized tools (surveys, interview and focus group guides) were used across sites to allow cross-country comparison.

Survey studies were conducted among rehabilitation professionals (e.g. a baseline study in Rwanda with approximately 60 physiotherapists) to capture their prior experience with digital tools and their perceptions after using Physitrack in practice [6, 7, 8]. Semi-structured interviews and focus groups were conducted with Rwandan and Indonesian CHWs, patients and providers to understand usability, acceptability, and challenges of the digital-first approach [9]. Technical data from the app (e.g. number of exercise sessions completed, user adherence rates) were monitored to further understand engagement. A comparative study examined the health outcomes of Rwandan patients receiving traditional hospital physiotherapy versus those using the digital pathway facilitated by CHWs. This included applying a standard quality-of-life instrument (EQ-5D-5L) and calculating quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) for each group over an equivalent follow-up period. Cost data were analyzed from the health system perspective to compare resource use in each pathway [10].

Throughout, the project maintained an adaptive management approach. Monthly coordination meetings and open co-working sessions were held (often virtually) among JAMK, the companies, and international focal points to monitor progress, share lessons, and solve challenges in real time. Especially when minor deviations from the original plan occurred.

Global Dissemination & Engagement (WP4)

From the start, the project implemented a robust dissemination strategy to build acceptance for digital rehabilitation innovation. A communication plan was developed early, and an external communications firm was engaged to shape key messages for a global audience. The project launched the Global Digital Rehabilitation Initiative as an open knowledge-sharing platform, which by 2024 had attracted over 180 experts from more than 30 countries. Through this initiative, the team organized regular webinars and virtual forums (including a series of monthly online sessions in early 2024) for discussing project results, demonstrating digital rehabilitation tools, and gathering input from the international rehabilitation community. These events drew around 300 participants worldwide, indicating substantial interest. The project also circulated a Digital Rehabilitation newsletter to hundreds of subscribers, highlighting progress and interim results in an accessible format.

Coordination with the World Health Organization and other international bodies was a deliberate part of the methodology. For example, the project lead and researchers presented updates during WHO forums (such as the Geneva Digital Health Day). This proactive engagement was intended to validate the project's approach through dialogue with global experts and to get a wider audience for sharing our findings. In summary, the implementation of DIRECT was characterized by co-creation with stakeholders, multinational research and pilots, continuous monitoring against the project plan, and strategic communication. The methodology stayed aligned with the approved plan's vision, with only minor adjustments (e.g. scheduling tweaks due to a later start and accommodating partners' needs). By the end of 2024, most planned activities and milestones had been completed, setting the stage for final analysis and reporting on the project's impact.

3. Key Achievements

The project yielded significant results, successfully translating its aims into tangible achievements. These include the development of new service models, generation of compelling initial evidence, stakeholder adoption, and contributions to global knowledge. The following are the key accomplishments of DIRECT.

Pioneering a Digital-First Rehabilitation Model

The project successfully designed and piloted a flexible digital-first rehabilitation service model for public healthcare settings. This conceptual model, co-created with health authorities and other key stakeholders, establishes a blueprint for delivering rehabilitation through a community-based digital approach into existing health services. In Rwanda, the model design and development was officially acknowledged by the Rwanda Biomedical Centre with support letter for its pilot implementation, including consultation with national task force to guide its development. By project's end, the model had been refined through real-world testing that could be adapted in Rwanda and other countries. This is a foundational achievement, demonstrating a viable approach to embed digital rehabilitation into health systems where traditional rehabilitation access is limited.

Expanding rehabilitation access

The interventions dramatically extended the availability of rehabilitation services in the target communities. For populations with little or no previous access to rehabilitation, the project provided digital rehabilitation via the Inclusion App and a CHW program. In Rwanda alone, over 2,000 patients (2,175 by late 2023) across three districts received rehabilitation exercise guidance and follow-up via the digital pathway during the pilot – these are individuals who otherwise might have waited months for a hospital appointment or gone untreated. Across all partner countries, the digital platforms and programs introduced by the project have reached more than 15,000 users to date. This number includes rural service users who accessed exercise programs through the app, many for the first time in their lives. Such scaling of rehabilitation access within a short period is a remarkable achievement, indicating the model's potential to rapidly close the treatment gap for common conditions than can lead to disability. As part of our research for future models, we also evaluated other technologies like conversational AI to learn about user interests and generate supporting evidence.

Improving health outcomes and efficiency

The project results demonstrate that a digital-first approach can, in certain instances, yield substantially better results and increase efficiency compared to traditional methods. In the comparative study focusing on patients with low back pain in Rwanda, those who followed the digital rehabilitation pathway (guided by the app and CHWs) were able to complete their rehabilitation in about one-third of the time of those in the conventional pathway (which involved multiple referrals and clinic visits). The median treatment duration fell from roughly 18 months (standard physiotherapy route) to 6 months with the digital approach, attributable to starting exercise programs earlier and fewer delays [10].

More importantly, health outcomes were superior: participants in the digital rehabilitation group achieved greater improvements in function and quality of life. When quantified in terms of quality-adjusted life years, the digital approach yielded approximately 1.38 QALYs gained per user versus 0.47 QALYs per patient for the standard pathway, nearly three times the health gain [10]. This reflects meaningful pain reduction and restored daily functioning for service users using the application. Moreover, these benefits were achieved with significantly fewer resources. The analysis revealed that the digital physiotherapy pathway was about seven times cheaper than the traditional approach, costing RWF 2,691 (US\$1.95) per patient compared to RWF 19,038 (US\$13.83)

[10]. These findings offer early real-world confirmation that digital rehabilitation can broaden access and deliver at least as good, if not better, results more affordably. Such evidence is crucial for policymakers and investors about the benefits of scaling up digital rehabilitation services.

Capacity Building and Workforce Empowerment through Task Shifting

Local rehabilitation professionals (physiotherapists and occupational therapists) in each target country were engaged and upskilled in digital service delivery. For example, over 150 Rwandan physiotherapists were introduced to the Physitrack/Physiotools platform and incorporated it into their clinical practice during the project, with many continuing to use the tool for prescribing home exercise programs to their clients. By the end of the project, roughly one-third of all licensed rehabilitation professionals in Rwanda had experienced using and test the digital platform. Similar capacity-building workshops in Kenya, Indonesia, and Vietnam established a core group of practitioners receptive to and supportive of expanding digital rehabilitation services. This empowerment of health workers at multiple levels is an important outcome, as it creates local champions for sustaining and scaling the innovation beyond the project's timeline. Overall, acceptance and interest in digital rehabilitation increased over the course of the project, and by the end, there was little resistance—even when task shifting occurred.

Additionally, a significant achievement of DIRECT has been the mobilization of non-specialist health workers to deliver rehabilitation, thereby strengthening the human resource base for rehabilitation in partner countries. The project trained dozens of CHWs (around 70 in Rwanda, 50 in Kenya and 40 in Indonesia) in rehabilitation need identification and the use of digital tools for guiding therapy. These workers have effectively taken on new competencies, under supervision of rehabilitation professionals, expanding the workforce capable of providing rehabilitation services.

Global Networking and Thought Leadership

Through WP4, DIRECT positioned itself and its partners as global thought leaders in the emerging field of digital rehabilitation. The project's Global Digital Rehabilitation Initiative grew into a vibrant network that facilitated knowledge exchange among international experts, companies, and health system stakeholders. By 2024, the Initiative had organized three high-profile global forums and published periodic newsletters, which together disseminated the project's insights to a worldwide audience. A final summit (the Global Digital Rehabilitation Summit in November 2024) convened stakeholders to share key findings and best practices. The keen interest evidenced by participation numbers in the hundreds is an achievement in itself – it indicates that DIRECT tapped into a real demand for dialogue on this topic. Moreover, the project directly engaged with the World Health Organization and related bodies. JAMK University of Applied Sciences, as the coordinator, became the only Finnish member of the new World Rehabilitation Alliance (a WHO-affiliated global network for rehabilitation), and a case study from DIRECT's Rwanda pilot was officially accepted by the Alliance for global sharing. During the project, JAMK also entered the process of becoming the world's first WHO Collaborating Centre for Digital Rehabilitation, underlining how the project's work has been recognized as globally significant. This level of international validation and leadership is a major achievement, amplifying the project's influence beyond its immediate interventions.

Research Outputs

The project generated valuable research outputs that will continue to inform academia, industry, and policy. These include a comprehensive understanding on digital rehabilitation readiness in partner countries and be-

yond, a case study, accepted by the World Rehabilitation Alliance, an ongoing scoping review of digital rehabilitation research in sub-Saharan Africa [11] to be completed in 2025 amongst others. The project documented its pilot results in reports and policy briefs. For example, an exploratory cost-effectiveness analysis report for Rwanda's Ministry of Health providing evidence to support decision-making. Project team members presented findings at international scientific conferences (e.g., ACRM Atlanta [11], AWP Indonesia, NCDHWS Finland [12], eHealth Finland [13]) and contributed to WHO consultations, thereby integrating project findings into wider discussions. The team's post-project work includes drafting several academic manuscripts on the pilots and digital-first model results for peer-reviewed publication. The main findings of the project will be presented in the World Physiotherapy Congress Tokyo, May 2025. The evidence base for digital rehabilitation in low-resource settings is notably strengthened by the findings emerging from this project.

In summary, the project achieved what it set out to do as it developed a disruptive service model and demonstrated its feasibility. The project measurably improved access and outcomes for populations in need and it was validated at national, regional, and global levels. These achievements position the project as a catalyst for change in how rehabilitation is delivered, creating a foundation that partners and stakeholders can build upon moving forward.

4. Embracing innovation and policy pathways

The success of the DIRECT project can also be measured by the degree of acceptance and validation it received from end-users, professionals, policymakers, and international stakeholders. Introducing a novel digital rehabilitation model requires not only proving the concept but also earning the trust of those who will use and support it. Throughout its course, the project observed increasing acceptance of digital rehabilitation in multiple domains, and its approach were validated through both formal evaluations and real-world endorsements.

User acceptance

In the communities where the project piloted its interventions, the response from clients and households was generally very positive. Many service users using the digital rehabilitation services found the approach convenient and empowering. Instead of having to travel long distances or wait long periods for rehabilitation, they were able to start exercises quickly at home under the guidance of CHWs. Qualitative feedback gathered in Rwanda indicated that service users appreciated being active participants in their recovery. Some users noted that the application's instructional videos and other features made them feel more confident performing exercises correctly and safely. In contrast, the standard care group often reported frustrations due to delays and limited therapy sessions. Moreover, there were no reports of serious negative consequences using the digital approach, and community leaders were supportive after observing positive changes in their community. CHWs effectively delivering a new service and patients embracing it, was a critical factor in demonstrating that the model is both culturally and logistically acceptable in low-resource settings.

Endorsement from social and healthcare professionals

The project generally got a strong buy-in from service providers and professional communities, which is essential for sustained adoption. In Rwanda, physiotherapists in the pilot districts collaborated with the project and provided oversight or referrals when needed. This was done through tele-rehabilitation set-up from clinics to rehabilitation hospitals. Initially, some practitioners were skeptical about digital tools or about non-specialists doing "their" work. However, as the pilot progressed, many of these professionals became advocates of the model and recognized its value. Main discussions related to task-shifting rather than use of technology. General acceptance towards use of digital technologies was high among professionals from the start. For example, the survey of Rwandan rehabilitation professionals revealed that a majority found Physitrack easy to use and felt it improved their efficiency in prescribing home exercise programs [5, 6]. Crucially, over 90% of those surveyed indicated they would like to continue using digital platforms in their practice even after the project.

The supportive supervision framework put in place by the project (where specialists mentor CHWs and review cases if needed) helped alleviate concerns by clarifying roles. Professionals saw that rather than being replaced, they could extend their reach through the digital model and focus their expertise where it's needed most. The endorsement of the concept was also evident in the enthusiasm of CHWs, who took pride in their new role and reported increased respect from community members. Health workers in multiple countries requested additional languages and content on the app to serve their populations better, indicating that they foresee continuous use [9]. Widespread support from healthcare workers indicates the model's scalability and likely smooth implementation.

Government approval

One of the most significant endorsements of the work came from government stakeholders. In Rwanda, the Ministry of Health not only permitted the study but became an active supporter through the Rwanda Biomedical Centre. An official letter endorsed the project's pilot program, recognizing it as an innovative approach in line with Rwanda's healthcare priorities. As results came in, Rwandan officials expressed interest in expanding the approach and integrating lessons learned into other strategies. The invitations for the project team to contribute to these discussions is a clear endorsement at policy level.

Inspired by its success, Tanzania's Ministry of Health contacted us to learn from our experiences, and we are now discussing similar pilot programs in Tanzanian districts—a testament to the model's regional appeal. In Kenya, county health officials who were briefed on the project expressed interest in using the digital approach to strengthen primary care services, particularly for managing the growing burden of non-communicable diseases. As the project concluded, Finnish government and Business Finland representatives in partner countries discussed how the project's results could shape future development cooperation and business opportunities. This indicates that funders and policymakers see the value in what was accomplished. The endorsement by authorities is further underscored by the willingness to accommodate the project and review future policies. Overall, gaining multi-country governmental buy-in for a novel concept within a short time frame is a strong sign of acceptance and an enabler for sustainability.

Real-World Evidence

The credibility of the approach has been substantiated through global consultations and multi-level discussions. The project's cost-effectiveness and outcomes analysis was conducted in collaboration with a health economics expert. The positive findings (increased QALYs and reduced costs) constitute real-world evidence, quantitatively demonstrating the model's efficacy and confirming the project's central hypothesis. We summarized these findings in a policy brief, widely shared with stakeholders. In 2025, JAMK will expand the research to Indonesia, replicating the study and verifying its previous findings.

Furthermore, this project aligns with WHO's Rehabilitation 2030, offering a viable model for integrating rehabilitation into primary care. Its case study, accepted by the World Rehabilitation Alliance, demonstrates the model's merit within the broader rehabilitation community. Positive feedback from external experts—including leading university academics and clinicians—during global webinars confirmed this, with many hailing digital-first rehabilitation as "the way forward" and sharing similar experiences. Numerous well-known universities and global organizations have contacted us to exchange knowledge, further signifying the project's impact and value.

User Testimonials and Championing

Another softer but important aspect of acceptance came in the form of testimonials and word-of-mouth advocacy. Rehabilitation service users who experienced the digital service often became informal ambassadors, telling others about the benefits. For example, one patient from Musanze, Rwanda, who recovered from chronic back pain through the app-based exercises, spoke at a local health event about her experience, crediting the program for enabling her to return to work. Such personal stories were captured in project newsletters and helped humanize the data for decision-makers. When the Uganda Association of Physiotherapists invited a Rwandan project representative to present at a regional conference in 2023, it demonstrated peer validation among professionals in neighboring countries. Essentially, those peers were saying "this is something valuable to learn from." Indeed, interest from Uganda in adopting the Physitrack platform emerged as a direct result of hearing about the Rwanda pilot's success. By the project's conclusion, multiple champions at different levels,

from CHWs to ministry officials and international NGOs, had shown interest to carry the work forward. This multilevel acceptance is a critical asset, because it means the idea of digital rehabilitation has taken root in the minds of those who will drive future implementation.

In conclusion, the project's approach have been broadly endorsed by the people and institutions that matter for long-term impact. Clients used and benefited from the services, health workers integrated the tools into their practice, and governments and global bodies recognized the approach as credible and valuable. This collective endorsement reduces the risks for scale-up as stakeholders have confidence in the model and are thus more likely to invest in and expand these digital rehabilitation services after the project ends. The foundation of trust and proof is one of its greatest legacies, as it transforms digital rehabilitation from an untested idea into an accepted component of social- and healthcare delivery.

5. The Paradigm Shift

DIRECT's experience illustrates a broader paradigm shift happening in rehabilitation, one that reimagines how and where care is delivered through digital technology and innovative service models. Traditional rehabilitation services have typically been facility-based, labor-intensive, and reactive, often accessible only in urban centers or specialist clinics. The paradigm has long been that a patient must come to the rehabilitation provider (usually a physiotherapist or similar specialist) for face-to-face sessions, which limits reach and timeliness of care. By demonstrating a digital-first, community-based rehabilitation model is feasible, this project transforms the current paradigm. This new approach uses technology to proactively connect clients with services integrated into primary care. The paradigm shift centers on providing rehabilitation in primary care and community settings, not just specialized facilities. This aligns with the global push to integrate rehabilitation into all levels of health systems and achieve universal health coverage.

In practice, this project demonstrated that basic rehabilitation exercise programs (e.g., guided therapeutic exercises for back pain, neck pain, arthritis, stroke aftercare, etc.) can be delivered effectively outside of traditional clinic settings. A decade ago, it would have been unthinkable, but now a CHW, with minimal training and a mobile device, can easily facilitate rehabilitation sessions at a patient's home or local health center. This represents a new model of care delivery: one where digital tools complement human resources (CHWs, general nurses) to provide a service that previously required a specialist's hands-on involvement. It's a shift from rehabilitation being a high-touch, one-to-one service to partly being a tech-augmented, one-to-many service. The impact of the paradigm shift is evident in the improved outcomes—more people served, faster access, and equal or better outcomes.

Another dimension of the paradigm shift is the empowerment of service users and families in the rehabilitation process. Digital platforms enable users to take a more active role in their own care. The Inclusion App, used in several studies, is a prime example: patients can see their exercise programs, give feedback, essentially putting knowledge and agency in their hands. As the example of Rwanda demonstrates, simply providing CHWs with the necessary devices enables the delivery of services, even when people lack such gadgets. Unlike the traditional model, this approach moves away from the therapist acting as the single expert in charge towards a model of self-management supported by digital technology. Clients become partners in their rehabilitation journey, guided remotely by professionals when needed. Because care is more continuous and personalized, this approach will improve patient adherence and health outcomes.

The project's results indicate a high level of engagement with digital care models among low-resource populations when design incorporates user-friendliness and cultural sensitivity. The role of the rehabilitation workforce is also transformed. Rather than viewing the limited number of physiotherapists as a ceiling for how many patients can receive care, the digital-first model treats specialist expertise as a resource that can be amplified. Skilled future therapists become supervisors, trainers, and complex-case consultants, while a broader base of social- and health workers and even the clients themselves deliver routine aspects of rehabilitation guided by digital services. This task-sharing model showcases the extended reach of primary care which now includes services such as maternal care or chronic disease follow-ups with telemedicine support from CHWs. Demonstrating the community health system's ability to effectively deliver rehabilitation exercises for simpler cases could shift rehabilitation workforce dynamics. It implies that countries could substantially increase coverage of rehabilitation services without waiting decades. This is possible by training existing CHWs, providing them with digital tools and support from specialist teams, thus avoiding the decades-long wait for additional therapists.

The project's success in Rwanda and elsewhere provides a viable model for restructuring the rehabilitation workforce pyramid: a small number of specialists can indirectly serve a large population through digital technology,

significantly improving efficiency. Data-driven continuous improvement is another aspect of this paradigm shift. In a digital rehabilitation model, every interaction (exercise done, pain level reported, goal achieved) can be recorded and analyzed. This creates a feedback loop for care improvement and for population health insights. The project, for example, got basic information on thousands of exercise sessions completed and their self-evaluated outcomes. In the future such data can form the basis for refining protocols (e.g. identifying which exercises yield the best results for certain demographics, or when clients tend to drop off the program so interventions can be timed accordingly). In the traditional paradigm, such amounts of data on rehabilitation processes and outcomes are rarely available or used systematically.

This approach is evidence-based, uses digital data collection to inform best practices and enable personalized adjustments. This paves the way for future rehabilitation services to utilize AI and data-driven decision support, optimizing individualized, multidisciplinary plans—a transformation enabled by the digitalization of rehabilitation. Perhaps the most profound shift underscored by the project is a change in perspective: that rehabilitation is not an auxiliary service but a fundamental and universal health service readily scalable for widespread delivery. Historically, rehabilitation in health systems has been sidelined or seen as a specialized niche (often under-resourced relative to curative services). The new paradigm, which the project contributes to, positions rehabilitation as an integral part of primary care, vital for early intervention and long-term disease and injury management. This project shows that digital community-based rehabilitation improves patient outcomes, benefits the healthcare system, and boosts the economy by preventing disability, reducing hospital readmissions, and speeding up return to work.

The paradigm shift isn't just technological; it also involves organizational and cultural changes. To widely adopt digital-first rehabilitation, healthcare systems need to update policies to include digital sessions in care plans and insurance coverage. We have initiated discussions in partner countries regarding policy adjustments, including the possibility of community health insurance covering digital rehabilitation. Rehabilitation is changing; providers and users need to embrace new approaches, such as a nurse using a tablet with a patient outdoors, instead of traditional hospital settings. This project is a successful example of the emerging cultural shift that others can reference.

To summarize, this project represents a fundamental change in rehabilitation, shifting from facility-based to community-based care, from analog to digital technologies, from specialist-led to team-based approaches, and from low to high-volume service delivery. This change reflects a larger global health trend: digital transformation is extending healthcare access to more people than ever (WHO). This project demonstrates a future of rehabilitation that is universally accessible, timely, and effective, thanks to innovative technology and human resources. Consolidating and expanding this new model will be key; the project's progress points to a major overhaul in how rehabilitation is conceived and provided.

6. Recommendations

Based on the DIRECT project findings, we propose recommendations and future steps to advance digital rehabilitation and sustainable impact. The recommendations are in line with both national and international health strategies. These recommendations target policymakers, healthcare providers, international agencies, and industry stakeholders responsible for implementing them.

6.1 Digital-first rehabilitation is effective and scalable

This project shows that a digital-first rehabilitation model is both feasible and cost-effective, scaling better than traditional methods. Digital rehabilitation delivered by CHWs in Rwanda yielded superior patient outcomes (1.38 vs. 0.47 QALYs) and faster treatment completion. The digital approach also proved significantly more cost-effective, costing roughly US\$2 per patient compared to US\$14 for traditional physiotherapy [10].

These results strongly support integrating digital-first rehabilitation into national health financing, including universal health coverage. Governments and development partners should view this model as a vital investment in expanding access to essential rehabilitation services, particularly in resource-limited areas.

6.2 Task-sharing and digital tools can bridge the workforce gap

The global shortage of rehabilitation professionals is a longstanding barrier to scale. The findings demonstrated that CHWs can safely deliver digital rehabilitation programs under the guidance of trained professionals. In the partner countries, over 100 CHWs were trained to provide effective, supervised digital rehabilitation using the Inclusion App.

This task-sharing model enables broader reach and better use of limited professional capacity. Countries should embed digital rehabilitation competencies into professional and community health training and prioritize task-sharing models in rehabilitation workforce strategies. Additionally, pilot programs should incorporate cognitive, speech, and mental health rehabilitation services, using the same community-based digital platform.

6.3 Local co-creation drives adoption and contextual fit

Overall success resulted from co-creation with local stakeholders—from participation or consultations with Ministries of Health to frontline CHWs and users themselves. This approach ensured that tools and service models were aligned with cultural norms, health system priorities, and implementation realities.

For global uptake, digital rehabilitation initiatives must adopt participatory design methods. Policymakers and funders should require that future implementations involve co-design with target users, which builds trust, ownership, and sustainability from the outset.

6.4 Global interest confirms readiness for paradigm shift

The Global Digital Rehabilitation Initiative demonstrated strong international interest for innovation in rehabilitation. Over 1,000 participants joined global events, and some national governments expressed interest in adopting digital-first models. The World Rehabilitation Alliance's recognition of the project's case study and engagement with global stakeholders and organizations confirms a readiness to move beyond pilot projects. To consolidate this shift, international agencies, regional bodies, and donors should support coordinated efforts to embed digital rehabilitation into global policy, training curricula, and rehabilitation service guidelines.

6.5 Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Evidence-Based Implementation

The project combined real-world testing and cost-effectiveness research to create stronger evidence base for national expansion. Using the FASTER framework [3], the project showed the potential effectiveness of the model. Future digital rehabilitation initiatives should follow similar models of user-centered approach on generating evidence on development, progressive usability and feasibility evaluation, and scaled evaluation and implementation.

AI also presents a significant opportunity to improve quality and efficiency as services scale. Refined LLMs can aid CHWs by assisting with identifying needs, and detecting red flags, thereby enabling earlier intervention and personalized care. In this model, CHWs aren't rehabilitation workers; instead, they're health promoters who identify needs and share digital content—playfully called "gadget holders"—to avoid increasing their workload.

6.6 Integration, not isolation, ready for scale

Digital rehabilitation should not operate in a silo as standalone service. DIRECT showed that combining community-based digital services with existing facility-based systems enables smoother referrals, oversight, and improved continuity of care. In Rwanda, health centers supported CHWs, and physiotherapists monitored progress.

To ensure long-term effectiveness, Ministries of Social and Health services should formally integrate digital-first models into care pathways and service packages. This involves updating service delivery, referrals, and health information systems, ensuring smoother data and user flows.

6.7 Private sector engagement and innovative models are key to sustainable growth

Working with the Finnish SMEs, Physiotools and CSE, was key to the project's success. These companies developed adaptable solutions, improved by real-world testing and feedback. Their involvement highlighted the importance of private sector innovation in social- and health system transformation.

Future digital rehabilitation efforts should engage companies from the outset. This includes exploring innovative business models such as public–private partnerships, subscription-based access, or telecom-supported service delivery. Blended financing and risk-sharing mechanisms can unlock new investment and sustain platform maintenance and evolution over time.

These recommendations provide a roadmap for stakeholders to begin a systemic overhaul of rehabilitation services. The project was a successful proof of concept. The task now is to replicate and expand these successes in a sustainable manner. The above steps, scaling proven models, broadening their scope, embedding them in policy and financing, empowering the workforce, integrating services, and continuing innovation, together form a comprehensive roadmap. This roadmap ensures the project's transformative impact on global healthcare is sustainable, making digital rehabilitation a standard practice and extending its reach to millions needing rehabilitation.

7. Conclusions

The DIRECT project has been a groundbreaking initiative at the intersection of digital innovation in social and healthcare, demonstrating how longstanding global health challenges can be addressed through creative, collaborative approaches. For three years, the project ambitiously aimed to revolutionize traditional rehabilitation services, creating a new model with far wider reach. Through these efforts, DIRECT has made significant contributions locally and internationally. The project has improved the lives of service users by providing previously inaccessible care and has generated significant knowledge and momentum beyond the project itself.

DIRECT's key finding is that digital-first rehabilitation is both feasible and highly effective in areas with limited resources. Real-world testing shows that common rehabilitation treatments delivered digitally can be as good as, or better than, traditional clinic-based treatments. The importance of this finding cannot be overemphasized: it will transform how health systems approach rehabilitation planning and resource allocation. Where a lack of specialists and infrastructure formerly left most patients without rehabilitation, a viable solution has emerged. Digital technology and community resources can greatly expand access to rehabilitation services, leading to better and more equitable health outcomes for the population.

This project highlights the crucial role of human-centered design and collaboration when implementing new digitally driven models. Local expertise, training, and continuous engagement were as crucial to the project's success as the technology itself. Because end-users (service users and frontline health workers) helped design the model, the resulting solutions were appropriate and user-friendly, leading to high uptake. Collaboration between the international team and local institutions fostered trust and ownership, key to long-term success.

From the Rwandan government's active participation to the enthusiasm of CHWs, it is clear that the project's collaborative approach created a sense of shared purpose. This highlights a general lesson: health innovation projects achieve more lasting impact when they co-create with stakeholders and embed their work within existing systems and communities.

The project results are broadly applicable and clear, complementing WHO strategies such as the Rehabilitation 2030 initiative and the expansion of digital health for universal health coverage. The problem of inadequate rehabilitation services transcends national income levels; it's prevalent in low- and middle-income countries and affects rural and marginalized communities in even high-income settings. Therefore, the solutions demonstrated by DIRECT have broad implications. This project's final report could guide policymakers and international agencies seeking to strengthen rehabilitation services. With a tested, evolving model, concrete early results, and practical implementation advice, the uncertainty surrounding digital rehabilitation adoption is reduced.

The project's contributions to global discourse is evident in the widespread interest generated by its research outputs, events, and the Global Digital Rehabilitation Initiative. We anticipate international adaptation and scaling of the model in the years ahead, partly due to this co-innovation project. From a sustainability perspective, the conclusion is encouraging. On one hand, the progress within the project's timeframe has been tremendous: by 2024, most of the DIRECT pilot sites had functioning digital rehabilitation pilots implemented, hundreds of professionals were engaged, and thousands of service users had benefited. Key institutions remain dedicated to this endeavor, and global partners, including WHO, are increasingly recognizing the importance of digital technologies in future rehabilitation models.

Sustaining the project's contributions necessitates sustained effort, resources, and enabling policies. The project highlighted the importance of ongoing focus on integrating digital rehabilitation funding into national budgets

and updating regulatory frameworks. To summarize, while the project established a solid foundation, realizing its full potential hinges on stakeholder commitment to the recommendations.

This project addressed a significant gap in rehabilitation access by implementing a novel digital service model; rigorous testing yielded results applicable to broader policy and practice. The project resonates well with the ethos of *“leapfrogging”* in global health, using technology and innovative models to bypass traditional limitations and accelerate progress. Rehabilitation, often termed the *“forgotten health service”*, has been brought to the forefront, proving that with the right approach, even complex health services can be redesigned for greater reach.

Finally, for external stakeholders, whether they are health officials, funding agencies, or innovators, the DIRECT project’s final message is one of possibility and urgency. It is possible to drastically improve access to rehabilitation through digital innovation and given the unmet need and the clear benefits demonstrated, it is urgent that we do so. By adopting and building upon the work of this initiative, stakeholders can contribute to a future where no person has to live with disability simply due to lack of access to therapy. The journey of DIRECT has shown the path; it is now up to the broader community to take the next bold steps on that path, ensuring that this pioneering effort translates into a global movement for inclusive and digitally empowered rehabilitation services.

References

- [1] A. Cieza, K. Causey, K. Kamenov, S. W. Hanson, S. Chatterji, and T. Vos, "Global estimates of the need for rehabilitation based on the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019," *The Lancet*, vol. 396, no. 10267, pp. 2006–2017, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(20)32340-0.
- [2] World Health Organization, "Rehabilitation 2030: A call for action." Accessed: Apr. 21, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/rehabilitation-2030-a-call-for-action>
- [3] R. H. Wang *et al.*, "The Time Is Now: A FASTER Approach to Generate Research Evidence for Technology-Based Interventions in the Field of Disability and Rehabilitation," *Arch. Phys. Med. Rehabil.*, vol. 102, no. 9, pp. 1848–1859, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2021.04.009.
- [4] World Rehabilitation Alliance, "Rehabilitation: a key strategy in addressing noncommunicable diseases." Accessed: May 02, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/documents/health-topics/rehabilitation/policy-brief-rehabilitation-a-key-strategy-in-addressing-ncds.pdf>
- [5] Oduor, Michael, "Rehabilitation Professionals' Attitudes Towards Technology Use and their Perspectives on Rehabilitation Services," Jamk Arena Public. Accessed: Feb. 28, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:jamk-issn-2984-0791-26>
- [6] M. Oduor, E. Aartolahti, and K. Korniloff, "Exploring Digital Rehabilitation: Perspectives of Rwandan Service Users and Professionals.," Jamk-arena. Accessed: Jan. 13, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:jamk-issn-2984-0791-163>
- [7] K. Lällä, M. Oduor, E. Aartolahti, D. Tumusiime, and K. Korniloff, "The relationship between attitudes, emotions and the intention to use the digital rehabilitation solution: Insights from Rwandan rehabilitation professionals," *Finn. J. EHealth EWelfare*, vol. 17, no. 1, Apr. 2025, doi: 10.23996/fjhw.153484.
- [8] E. Aartolahti, M. Oduor, D. Tumusiime, and K. Korniloff, "Rwandan Physiotherapists Experiences of a Digital Rehabilitation Solution: A Pilot Usability Study," *Arch. Phys. Med. Rehabil.*, vol. 105, no. 4, p. e166, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2024.02.583.
- [9] M. Oduor and E. Aartolahti, "Community Health Workers and Service Users' Experiences of a Community-based Digital Rehabilitation Application," Jamk-arena. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi:jamk-issn-2984-0791-74>
- [10] J. Kempers, J. D. Bigirimana, and K.-P. Murtonen, "Exploratory Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Digital Rehabilitation Services: Use of the Inclusion App for Persons with Low Back Pain in Rwanda.," 2025.
- [11] M. Oduor, K. Korniloff, J. Gasana, D. K. Tumusiime, and E. Aartolahti, "Digital Rehabilitation Interventions in Sub-Saharan Africa: Protocol for a Scoping Review," *JMIR Res. Protoc.*, vol. 12, p. e48952, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.2196/48952.
- [12] M. Oduor, E. Aartolahti, J. Gasana, Z. H. Faidullah, D. Tumusiime, and K. Korniloff, "Preliminary Findings from Community Health Workers' Experiences of a Digital Solution for Community-based Rehabilitation in Primary Healthcare," in *Särestöniemi, M., et al. Digital Health and Wireless Solutions: First Nordic Conference, NCDHWS 2024*, in Communications in Computer and Information Science (CCIS), vol. 2084. Oulu: Springer, p. 513.
- [13] Korniloff, Katariina, Oduor, Michael, Aartolahti, Eeva, Tumusiime, David, Tawa, Nassib, and Murtonen, Kari-Pekka, "Digital-First Rehabilitation Model for Inclusive and Accessible Primary Health Care in Low-resource Settings.," in *Conference book eHealth2023. Finnish Society of Telemedicine and eHealth.*, 2023. Accessed: Oct. 14, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.telemedicine.fi/images/pdf/seminaarit/2023/978-962-69224-8-5.pdf>